

Business Education in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: Cultivating Critical Thinking and Digital Citizenship

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17232753>

Abstract

In the era of Artificial Intelligence (AI), business education must evolve to equip students with critical thinking skills and responsible digital engagement necessary for success in a technology-driven world. This study examined the role of business and entrepreneurship education programme in promoting critical thinking and digital citizenship among undergraduates in universities in South-South, Nigerian. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, targeting a population of 81,230 undergraduates enrolled in business and entrepreneurship education programmes across thirty-two accredited universities in South-South, Nigeria. Where the multistage sampling technique was used to select sample size of 438 second year (200 level) students across 6 selected universities using a self-structured questionnaire that was validated by three experts. The questionnaire yielded a reliability coefficient score of 0.74 and 0.76 for sections B and C subscales respectively. The data obtained in the study was analyzed using descriptive and ANOVA statistics. Findings revealed that while business education curricula address critical thinking to a moderate extent ($M = 2.59/4.00$), there is a gap in the extent of integration of critical thinking to meet the demands of the AI age ($M = 2.13/4.00$), hence, it is not comprehensive enough. Furthermore, the promotion of digital citizenship among students was found to be low ($M = 2.43/4.00$), with gaps in areas such as digital responsibility, online ethics, and awareness of digital rights. The study concluded that critical thinking development remains largely theoretical, with limited practical application in AI scenarios, hence, significant improvements are needed to fully align with the evolving digital landscape. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Nigerian universities should revise the business education curriculum to explicitly integrate critical thinking components relevant to AI technologies. Additionally, universities should be mandated to implement structured programmes that promote digital citizenship, focusing on ethical digital behaviour, privacy, and online accountability.

Keywords: Business education, Artificial Intelligence (AI), critical thinking, digital citizenship, curriculum innovation.

Introduction

The advent of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) age has revolutionized global industries, necessitating a paradigm shift in educational approaches, particularly in business education. AI technologies, such as machine learning and data analytics, have become integral in business operations, demanding that business education graduates possess not only technical skills but also the ability to think critically and act responsibly in digital environments as emphasized by Yoromar (2024). Consequently, business education programmes must evolve to cultivate critical thinking and digital citizenship, preparing students to navigate and lead in an AI-driven world. In Nigeria, where tertiary institutions are increasingly integrating digital tools, the alignment of business education curricula with AI-driven competencies remains inconsistent (Adeoye et al., 2022). This gap raises concerns about business education graduates' preparedness for a labour market where AI literacy and ethical digital engagement are paramount.

Critical thinking is a cornerstone of effective decision-making and problem-solving in the business context. In the AI age, where information is abundant and rapidly changing, the ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information becomes even more crucial. In the context of business education, critical thinking in AI entails the ability to analytically evaluate AI-driven insights, question algorithmic biases, and assess the ethical implications of AI applications in decision-making. According to UNESCO (2023) critical thinking in AI involves cultivating a mindset that scrutinizes data sources, understands model limitations, and discerns between correlation and causation in AI outputs. Furthermore, critical thinking in AI demands digital literacy to navigate AI tools responsibly, ensuring alignment with organizational values and societal norms. This skill is vital for fostering informed, ethical, and adaptive leaders in an AI-augmented business landscape (Nguyen et al., 2023). Business education curricula must, therefore, be designed to foster analytical reasoning, encouraging students to question assumptions, assess evidence, and develop well-founded conclusions. A study by Alonta et al. (2024) highlighted concerns that AI might impede critical thinking by promoting surface-level learning, emphasizing the need for curricula that actively engage students in higher-order thinking tasks. This research seeks to assess the extent to which current business education programs in Nigerian universities incorporate elements that promote critical thinking in an AI-driven world.

Digital citizenship encompasses the responsible and ethical use of technology, a vital skill in today's interconnected digital landscape. According to World Economic Forum (2023) digital citizenship involves understanding data privacy, algorithmic transparency, intellectual property rights, online communication etiquette, and the societal impacts of AI-driven systems. Additionally, digital citizenship involves advocating for AI literacy, addressing digital divides, and engaging in discourse on AI's societal implications (Mbah & Ajayi, 2023). By cultivating digital citizenship capabilities, future business leaders can harness AI as a force for sustainable innovation while upholding democratic and human-centric values in the digital economy. As business operations increasingly rely on digital platforms, students must understand the implications of their online actions, including issues related to privacy, security, and digital etiquette. Business education programmes have a responsibility to instill these values, ensuring that graduates can navigate digital environments ethically and effectively. Otamiri and Deborah (2023), emphasized the importance of digital citizenship in enhancing the job effectiveness of business education lecturers, suggesting that similar benefits could extend to students. This study therefore assessed the extent to which business education programmes in universities in South-South of Nigeria, promote critical thinking and digital citizenship among their students.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into various sectors has significantly transformed business operations, necessitating a corresponding evolution in business education (World Economic Forum, 2023). Equally pressing is the issue of digital citizenship, which involves responsible and informed participation in digital environments. As business operations increasingly shift online, students must learn to engage ethically with digital tools and platforms, understanding issues related to data privacy, digital rights, and online behaviour. However, business education programmes seem to provide limited instruction in this area, leaving students ill-equipped to address ethical dilemmas and societal implications of digital technologies. This oversight is particularly troubling given the potential misuse of AI technologies, which can perpetuate bias and misinformation. Consequently, the development of digital citizenship remains a neglected yet vital aspect of preparing students for the future of work. Also, the absence of structured approaches to foster critical thinking within business education curricula undermines students' ability to navigate the complexities of contemporary professional life. Hence, it is therefore expedient to assess how universities in South-South of Nigerian are adapting business education to cultivate these essential skills, addressing two specific objectives: the promotion of critical thinking and digital citizenship in an AI-mediated learning environment.

Objective of the Study

The specific objectives of this study include:

1. to examine the extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.
2. to assess the level at which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. to what extent do business education curricula promote critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria?
2. to what extent do business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigerian?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education programme promotes digital citizenship.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. This design was considered appropriate for this study because this study entails a description of the phenomenon of critical thinking and digital citizenship in this era of AI as they exist in their natural setting at the time of research. The population of the study comprised of 81,230 second year undergraduates in business and entrepreneurship education programmes enrolled in 2024/2025 academic session across thirty-two accredited universities that offers business and entrepreneurship education programmes in South-South region of Nigeria.

The sample size for the study comprised of 438 second year (200 level) students in Business and Entrepreneurship Education Programmes across six selected universities in South-South, Nigeria. The sample size was derived from the Taro Yamane formular for determining sample size of known population as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n = sample size =?

N = population = 81,230

e = degree of precision = 0.05 (at 95% confidence level)

$$n = \frac{81,230}{1 + 81,230 (0.05)^2}$$

Hence; n = 398.04

Multistage sampling technique was used to select six of the Universities out of the available universities by using all the 200 level students in each of the institutions, the first stage (primary stage) of the multi-stage random selection process involves selecting discrete clusters from the sample elements (tertiary Universities in South-South, Nigeria) to form the primary sampling units (PSU). Therefore, the PSU include randomly selecting two hundred level students of six Universities (that is, 19%) out of the thirty-two accredited tertiary institutions offering business and entrepreneurship education programmes in South-South, Nigeria. The six institutions were selected through random techniques using a ballot system and they included University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State; 121 students, Ambrose Alli University (AAU), Ekpoma, Edo State; 95 students, University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross-river State; 119 students, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Rivers State; 79 students, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State; 81 students, and Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State; 43 students, which made up a total of 538 two hundred level students. However, this number was considered okay, since it is above the calculated sample size. The second stage (secondary sampling units, SSU) of multistage sampling involves selecting subgroups according to faculty of education from the 6 selected institutions. The tertiary stage (tertiary sampling units, TSU) involves selecting from the SSU, students in the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship education while the final stage (ultimate sampling units, USU) involves selecting from the TSU, registered full-time undergraduates in two hundred level only. The distribution of the sample size for data collection was shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Sample size for data collection

PSU (Undergraduates across 6 Tertiary Institutions in South-South, Nigeria)	SSU (Faculty of Education)	TSU (Department of Business/ Entrepreneurship education)	USU (total 200L students = 538)
University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State = 52, 000 students	5,882 students	100L = 164 students 200L = 121 students 300L = 115 students 400L = 97 students Total = 497 students	200L: 121/538 x 438 = 99
Ambrose Alli University (AAU), Ekpoma, Edo State = 38,000 students	3,900 students	100L = 101 students 200L = 95 students 300L = 84 students 400L = 69 students Total = 349 students	200L: 95/538 x 438 = 77
University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross-river State = 40,645 students	4,215 students	100L = 132 students 200L = 119 students 300L = 111 students 400L = 91 students Total = 453 students	200L: 119/538 x 438 = 97
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Rivers State = 28,000 students	2,920 students	100L = 86 students 200L = 79 students 300L = 65 students 400L = 52 students Total = 282 students	200L: 79/538 x 438 = 64
Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State = 22,000 students	2,775 students	100L = 84 students 200L = 81 students 300L = 77 students 400L = 71 students Total = 313 students	200L: 81/538 x 438 = 66
Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State = 20,275 students	2,140 students	100L = 52 students 200L = 43 students 300L = 41 students 400L = 38 students Total = 174 students	200L: 43/538 x 438 = 36
Total sample size for data collection			438

Source: Researcher's computation from available data in the selected universities' admin Offices

The research instrument of the study was a self-structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was structured into three sections A, B and C. Section A was made to collect demographic data of the Institutions such as the name of the Universities. Section B was made to collect data on the level of Business curricula on how it promotes critical thinking in this current dispensation of AI. Section C was made to collect data on the level of Business Education curricula on how it promotes digital citizenship in the era of AI. Section B and C contained seven (7) items respectively addressing the research questions. The response options for the questionnaire were 4-point Likert scale of: High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VL) which was validated by three experts in the field of study. The internal consistency method of reliability was used in this study, as such; the Cronbach's alpha reliability technique was used to compute the reliability coefficient of the instrument. Using the study's research instrument, trial test was carried out among ten percent of the sample size, that is, forty-four (44) undergraduates in Business and Entrepreneurship Education programme, which was not part of the sample size but were part of the study population. After computation was carried using Cronbach's alpha reliability technique in SPSS data analytical software (version 26.0); the instrument yielded reliability scores of 0.74 and 0.76 for sections B and C subscales respectively (see appendix II). Six research assistants, one from each of the six selected universities, participated in the collection of data. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, mean and standard deviation. Also, the stated hypotheses were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics, which was set at a level of significance of 0.05.

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: *To what extent do business education curricula promote critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria?*

Table 2 showed the result of participants' responses as regards the level of extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing the level of extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	The current business education curriculum in my university explicitly includes courses that teach critical thinking skills in relation to AI applications.	438	2.32	.901	Low Extent
2	The business education curriculum encourages me to analyze information critically before making decisions.	438	3.11	.813	High Extent
3	Assignments and projects in my business education courses often require me to solve real-world problems using logical reasoning.	438	2.82	.755	Moderate Extent
4	My coursework frequently involves tasks that enhance my ability to think independently.	438	2.77	.924	Moderate Extent
5	Lecturers in my programme emphasize the development of critical thinking skills during AI-related topics or discussions.	438	2.58	.888	Moderate Extent
6	I am regularly exposed to case studies and scenarios that require in-depth analysis.	438	2.07	.780	Low Extent
7	The overall structure and delivery of the business education curriculum in my university promote critical inquiry.	438	2.48	.816	Low Extent
Aggregate Mean		438	2.59	0.84	Moderate Extent

Note: N (Sample Size), M (Mean), SD (Standard Deviation)

Level of extent: low extent ($M < 2.50$), moderate extent ($M = 2.50 - 2.99$), high extent ($M \geq 3.00$)
In response to the level of extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI, Table 2 showed the mean ratings of items 1 to 7 ranged from 2.07 to 3.11 while the standard deviations ranged from 0.755 to 0.924. The mean ratings showed that 3 out of the seven item statements were given moderate ratings, one item was rated as high while 3 items were rated low. The aggregate mean showed a mean of 2.59 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.84. With these results, it showed that there is a moderate extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria?*

Table 3 showed the results of participants' responses to the level of extent to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics showing the level of extent to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI.

S/N	Items	N	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Business education programme in my school explicitly teaches ethical guidelines for using AI tools.	438	2.41	.714	Low Extent
2	My lecturers regularly emphasize the importance of verifying AI-generated information before applying it to business decisions or assignments.	438	2.37	.769	Low Extent
3	My programme includes training on digital rights (e.g., copyright laws, ethical AI use) relevant to modern business environments.	438	2.25	.695	Low Extent
4	I feel equipped by my business education to navigate digital spaces with social awareness.	438	2.51	.701	Moderate Extent
5	Course content in my school includes discussions on digital responsibilities, and respectful online engagement.	438	2.49	.863	Low Extent
6	I have been taught about online privacy, and data protection in my courses.	438	2.55	.799	Moderate Extent
7	My programme equips me with knowledge on how to identify and avoid digital manipulation.	438	2.40	.705	Low Extent
Aggregate Mean		438	2.43	0.75	Low Extent

Note: N (Sample Size), M (Mean), SD (Standard Deviation)

Level of extent: low extent ($M < 2.50$), moderate extent ($M = 2.50 - 2.99$), high extent ($M \geq 3.00$)

In response to the level of extent to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI, Table 3 showed the mean ratings of items 1 to 7 ranged from 2.25 to 2.55 while the standard deviations ranged from 0.695 to 0.863. The mean ratings showed that only 2 out of the seven item statements were given high ratings while 5 items were rated low. The aggregate mean showed a mean of 2.43 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.75. With these results, it showed that there is a low level of extent to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Testing of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis I: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected Universities in South-South on the extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking.

Table 4: ANOVA statistics showing results for the significant difference in the extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking among students across the 6 selected universities in South-South, Nigeria.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	81.555	3	52.411	1.491	.244
Within Groups	111.287	434	.581		
Total	192.842	437			

Result: $F(3, 434) = 1.491, p = 0.244$. Results of the one-way ANOVA statistics carried out to test hypothesis 1 showed that the test do not have a significant p-value at the 5% level of significance.

Since the calculated p-value of (.244) was greater than 0.05, we failed to reject the null hypothesis. We therefore conclude that There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected Universities in South-South on the extent to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking.

Hypothesis II: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education programme promotes digital citizenship.

Table 5: ANOVA analysis showing results for the significant difference in the level at which business education programme promote digital citizenship among students across the 6 selected universities in South-South, Nigeria.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Subjects	238.575	3	48.370	.0111	.315
Within Subjects	770.400	434	80.901		
Total	1008.975	437			

Result: $F = 0.0111, p = 0.315$.

Results displayed in table 4 showed that the p-value that is .315 associated with the test statistics (ANOVA statistics) was greater than 0.05, thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Hence, the study concluded that There is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education programme promotes digital citizenship. Hence, difference does not exist in the responses of sampled students across the 6 selected universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Study findings for research question one revealed that there is a moderate extent (Mean = 2.59/4.00) to which business education curricula promotes critical thinking in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. However, gaps were found to exist in areas such as students' exposure to case studies and scenarios that require in-depth analysis and critical reflection (Mean = 2.07/4.00), the inclusion of courses that teach critical thinking skills in relation to AI applications (Mean = 2.32/4.00), and lastly, the promotion of critical inquiry and reflective thinking (Mean = 2.48/4.00). In support of this finding, a study by Alonta et al. (2024) highlighted concerns that the current business education curricula might impede critical thinking by promoting surface-level learning, emphasizing the need for curricula that actively engage students in higher-order thinking tasks.

The findings of research question two revealed that there is a low level of extent (Mean = 2.43/4.00) to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. Respondents were found to lack ethical guidelines for using AI tools (Mean = 2.41/4.00), training on digital rights and responsibilities (Mean = 2.25/4.00) as well as the knowledge on how to identify and avoid misinformation and digital manipulation (Mean = 2.40/4.00). This finding is in line with a study carried out by Adeoye et al. (2022), which revealed that in Nigeria where tertiary institutions are increasingly integrating digital tools, the alignment of business education curricula with AI-driven competencies in digital citizenship remains inconsistent.

Analysis of hypothesis one revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education curricula

promotes critical thinking in this era of AI, was accepted. This was buttressed in the study of Alonta et al. (2024), disclosed that the current business education curricula might impede critical thinking by promoting surface-level learning, this implies that there is need for curricula that actively engage students in higher-order thinking tasks with the use of AI in business education to equip students with critical thinking skills with digital competencies.

The second null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of the 6 selected universities in South-South on the extent to which business education programme promotes digital citizenship was equally accepted. This indicated that there is a low extent to which business education programme promote digital citizenship in this era of AI among students in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. Respondents were found to lack ethical guidelines for using AI tools, training on digital rights, digital awareness or manipulation. This was discovered by the study of Adeoye et al. (2022), who affirmed that in Nigeria where tertiary institutions are increasingly integrating digital tools, the alignment of business education curricula with AI-driven proficiencies in digital citizenship still lack consistency.

Conclusion

This study examined the extent to which business education curricula in universities in South-South Nigerian promote critical thinking and digital citizenship in the era of artificial intelligence. The findings showed that while business education programmes demonstrated a moderate emphasis on critical thinking, there is a significant deficiency in fostering digital citizenship. This suggests that curriculum developers and educators have made considerable efforts to integrate critical thinking into teaching and learning activities in business education programmes (Yoromar & Wagbara, 2021). However, there remains room for improvement in deepening students' engagement with critical thinking tasks. Also, students appear to lack adequate training in digital ethics, data privacy, and online engagement. This shortfall may hinder students' capacity to function as responsible digital citizens in professional settings. The study concluded that critical thinking development in business education programmes remains largely theoretical, with limited practical application in AI scenarios, whereas, the fostering of comprehensive digital citizenship among students was deficient. Significant improvements will be essential for producing graduates who are well-prepared for the cognitive demands of the digital age.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion arrived at the study, it was recommended that:

1. The National Universities Commission (NUC) should mandate the inclusion of standalone digital citizenship courses in business education programmes, covering AI ethics, data privacy, cybersecurity, and responsible AI use. These modules should adopt interactive pedagogies like case studies on AI problems (e.g., algorithmic bias, deepfakes) to bridge the identified gap in the study.
2. The Federal Ministry of Education should sponsor annual AI-ethics training workshops for business educators, equipping them with tools to teach digital citizenship effectively. Partnerships with tech firms (e.g., Google, Microsoft) could provide practical frameworks for embedding ethical AI discussions in existing courses like Business Ethics and ICT.
3. While critical thinking is moderately emphasized, university senates should rebalance curricula by reviewing course outcomes so as to upgrade contents of critical thinking and digital responsibility in line with current AI age.
4. State governments in the South-South region should fund university-based AI policy labs where business education students collaborate with ICT experts to develop localized digital

citizenship charters. These labs would foster hands-on learning while producing actionable policies for responsible AI use in enterprises within South-South region of Nigeria.

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APPENDIX I

QUESTIONNAIRE ON BUSINESS EDUCATION IN THE ERA OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: CULTIVATING CRITICAL THINKING AND DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP

SCHOOL OF GENERAL STUDIES,
NIGERIA MARITIME UNIVERSITY,
OKERENKOKO,
DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Your Institution:

- a. University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State [];
- b. Ambrose Alli University (AAU), Ekpoma, Edo State [];
- c. Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [];
- d. Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State [];
- e. University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross-river State [];
- f. Niger Delta University, Amassoma, Bayelsa State []

SECTION B: LEVEL OF BUSINESS EDUCATION CURRICULA PROMOTING CRITICAL THINKING IN THIS ERA OF AI

Please indicate the extent of your agreement to the following items in the table below:
Key: Very High Extent = VHE; High Extent = HE; Low Extent = LE; and Very Low Extent = VLE

	Items	HE			VLE
	The current business education curriculum in my university explicitly includes courses that teach critical thinking skills in relation to AI applications.				
	The business education curriculum encourages me to analyze and evaluate information critically before making decisions.				
	Assignments and projects in my business education courses often require me to solve real-world problems using logical reasoning.				
	My coursework frequently involves tasks that enhance my ability to think independently and question assumptions.				
	Lecturers in my programme emphasize the development of critical thinking skills during AI-related topics or discussions.				

	I am regularly exposed to case studies and scenarios that require in-depth analysis and critical reflection.				
	The overall structure and delivery of the business education curriculum in my university promote critical inquiry and reflective thinking.				

SECTION C: LEVEL OF BUSINESS EDUCATION CURRICULA PROMOTING DIGITAL CITIZENSHIP IN THIS ERA OF AI

Please indicate the extent of your agreement to the following items in the table below:
 Key: Very High Extent = VHE; High Extent = HE; Low Extent = LE; and Very Low Extent = VLE

	Items	HE			VLE
	Business education programme in my school explicitly teaches ethical guidelines for using AI tools.				
	My lecturers regularly emphasize the importance of verifying AI-generated information before applying it to business decisions or assignments.				
	My programme includes training on digital rights and responsibilities (e.g., copyright laws, ethical AI use) relevant to modern business environments.				
	I feel equipped by my business education to navigate digital spaces with integrity, accountability, and social awareness.				
	Course content in my school includes discussions on digital rights, responsibilities, and respectful online engagement.				
	I have been taught about online privacy, data protection, and responsible sharing of information in my courses.				
	My programme equips me with knowledge on how to identify and avoid misinformation and digital manipulation.				

APPENDIX II

SECTION B

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	44	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	44	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardize		
Cronbach's Alpha	d Items	N of Items
0.74	.713	7

SECTION C

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	44	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	44	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardize		
Cronbach's Alpha	d Items	N of Items
.760	.754	7